

Investigation of the influence of active cooling on battery cell testing

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Abstract— In this article we investigate the influence of the direct cooling strategy on battery cell testing. We investigate the influence on entropy, hybrid pulse power test and fast charge tests. We compare two strategies for temperature control during testing. The first strategy is air cooling and uses a conventional temperature chamber. The second strategy is an active cooling strategy using a fluid-based cooling system. In the course of our analysis, we investigate the influence on test duration, accuracy and reproducibility. Results show that the time needed to adjust different cell surface temperatures can be significantly reduced by active cooling. Furthermore, results indicate, that also the reproducibility can be improved by changing the cooling method.

I. INTRODUCTION

Batteries are a key technology in the transition of our energy system and the mobility sector towards renewable energy sources. Battery testing is required during battery development to determine key battery characteristics needed for system design and battery management. The testing must be reliable and fast to meet high safety standards and reduce the cost of battery development. [1]

One of the most important factors in battery testing is precise temperature control during the test [2]. In addition, the battery has a high thermal mass and a rather low temperature conductivity between the electrode layers. Setting a new temperature within a test is often very time consuming [3]. Finally, in real-world operating scenarios, the battery does not experience a constant temperature, but rather significant temperature changes due to internal heating and external cooling. This has significant effects on performance and aging and can also lead to path-dependent degradation phenomena [4]. Therefore, it is expected that the study of temperature will become even more important in the future, and therefore advanced methods of temperature control are required.

Temperature control can be realized by different strategies [5]. Air cooling and active cooling are two possible solutions. For air cooling using a temperature chamber, it is well known that the positioning within the chamber has an influence on the temperature and consequently on the test results [6,7]. This can be overcome with an active cooling system where the surface temperature of a cell is directly controlled by a fluid cooling system.

In this paper we investigate the effect of two different cooling strategies for temperature control during battery testing. The first strategy uses conventional air-cooling temperature control with temperature chambers. The second

strategy uses an active cooling strategy. We investigate the influence of these strategies for three basic battery tests: 1st, entropy test [8], 2nd, hybrid pulse power capability (HPPC) test [9], and 3rd, fast charge test. We investigate the influence of the strategy on the duration, reliability, and reproducibility of the test.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Measurement Setups

Figure 1: Different test configurations used.

We use two different measurement setups. The first setup is a conventional air-cooled setup using a temperature chamber and a battery test system. Within this setup, we vary the position and mounting of the battery cells. Configuration 1 and configuration 3 are positioned parallel to the front door. Configuration 2 and configuration 4 are positioned normally. In addition, configurations 1 and configurations 2 are free standing and do not use a cell fixture, while configurations 3 and 4 use the same cell fixture as configurations 5-12 in the second setup. The second setup uses an active cooling strategy employing the ACORA test system from AVL List GmbH. Within this setup, the temperature of the cell is controlled from two sides, i.e. the large sides of the cell as shown in Figure 2A, using a water – glycol (42/58 %) based liquid cooling jacket. The inlet of the cooling plates is controlled with setting one temperature and one flow, split up to each individual cell. The flow was set to 5 liter per minute per cell and the heat ramp was limited to 5 Kelvin per minute. The system can test eight cells in parallel. These are positioned in two rows with 4 cells in each row. Configurations 5-8 are positioned at positions 1-4 in row 1, i.e. R1P1, R1P2, R1P3 and R1P4, and configurations 9-12 in

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row 2, i.e. R2P1, R2P2, R2P3 and R2P4. This can also be seen in Figure 2B.

Figure 2: (A) Test cell, (B) Positions within the ACORA test system.

The cells are equipped with temperature sensors. The location and number of the sensors varies. Cells are equipped with 1 to 18 sensors.

B. Test scenarios and protocols

The first test conducted is an entropy test, the second test is a HPPC test, and the third test is a fast charge test. Details of the test protocols are given below.

Figure 3: Set temperatures for the 10h rest entropy test sequence.

The entropy test is performed on three different states of charge (SOC). To adjust the SOC, the cell capacity is measured. Then the SOC is adjusted and a rest period of 25 h at 25 °C is applied. The entropy test sequence is then started. We performed two entropy test sequences, one using a rest time of 5 h in each temperature point. The second uses a 10 h rest at each temperature point. The 10 h sequence is shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that a temperature sequence of 25-45-5-25 °C is used. This results in a total test duration of 40 hours. The test is performed at SOCs corresponding to 80 %, 50 % and 30 %. Entropy is evaluated by measuring the change in voltage for a given change in temperature. The entropy corresponds to the voltage change as

$$s = F \frac{dV}{dT}$$

where s is the entropy, dV/dT is the voltage gradient and F is the Faraday constant. Ideally, the voltage is evaluated after relaxation. However, this can be very time consuming, especially for active materials that tend to have very slow relaxation, such as LFP. Here the voltage after 10 h relaxation is used, i.e. at 10 h, 20 h and 30 h. The voltage gradient is then determined by linear regression.

The HPPC test is also performed at various SOCs in 10 % SOC increments. All tests were performed at 25 °C. During the HPPC test, a constant current discharge pulse is first applied for 30 s. This is followed by a rest period of 40-43 s.

Then a constant current (CC) regen pulse is applied for 40 s. The discharge and regen pulse use a C-rate of 1.5 C and 1 C respectively. An example result is shown in Figure 4. The procedure has been modified for SOC 100 %, 90 %, 80 % and 70 %. For those SOC points, the charge current was restricted because of the cell specific safety limits. According to this, the current magnitude was adjusted to match the safe range, specified by the cell manufacturer. The HPPC test is evaluated by calculating the discharge resistance as

$$R_{\text{discharge}} = \frac{V_1 - V_0}{I_1 - I_0}$$

Accordingly, the resistance is calculated as

$$R_{\text{regen}} = \frac{V_3 - V_2}{I_3 - I_2}$$

Figure 4: Example measurement for the performed HPPC test profile. Finally, a fast charge test is performed. Here, the cell was discharged to its final discharge voltage and afterwards charged with its maximum allowed C-Rate, i.e. 1 C, up to SOC 60 %.

C. Test cells

As cell a CALB LFP graphite prismatic cell with a nominal capacity of 125 Ah has been used. The cell model is L173F125A. The active material at the positive electrode is LiFePO₄

Table 1: Duration to reach T_1 and T_2 and standard deviation at these time points for different configurations.

Config. Nb.	T1 / h	T2 / h	$\sigma@T1 / K$	$\sigma@T2 / K$
1	0.67	2.71	1.19	0.16
2	0.7	-	0.48	-
3	0.96	2.33	2.36	0.16
4	1.23	4.43	0.67	0.33
8	0.13	0.44	0.44	0.12
9	0.12	0.39	0.39	0.11

Figure 5: Results for temperature change from 25 °C to 45 °C during the entropy test for configuration 3 and configuration 8 as an example for an air-cooled (A) and an active-cooled system (B), respectively. Times to reach a control voltage difference of 3 °C and 1 °C are given in the diagrams.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Entropy test

First, the test results for the entropy test are discussed. Figure 5 shows the surface temperature for configuration 3, which is air cooled, and configuration 8, which is actively

Figure 6: Voltage change after changing the set temperature from 25 °C to 45 °C for configuration 1-4, 8 and 9 at SOC 80 %, 50 %, and 30 %.

Figure 7: Voltage after relaxation for different set temperatures at 50 % SOC

cooled. The figure shows the range between the maximum and minimum measured temperature, the individual temperature sensors, and the average temperature. The results are shown for a change in the set temperature from 25 to 45 °C. The set temperature, 45 °C, is shown as a dashed black line. In addition, a temperature difference of 1 °C and 3 °C are shown as dark and light gray areas, respectively. It can be seen, that the surface temperature can be adjusted much faster in an actively cooled system. Specifically, a temperature difference of less than 3 °C is reached in 0.13 hours for configuration 8 and in 0.96 hours for configuration 3. This corresponds to a time reduction of approximately 86 %. Similarly, the time to reach a temperature difference of only 1 °C is reduced from 2.24 h to only 0.44 h.

Table 1 shows the evaluated times to reach T_1 and T_2 along with the standard deviation of the surface temperature sensors for configurations 1-4 and 8-9. The color indicates the relationship of the numbers within a column. It can be seen that in general the time to reach T_1 and T_2 is significantly lower for the active cooled system. It can also be seen that the standard deviation of the active cooled system is also

significantly lower, which may improve the reproducibility of the measurement results. It can also be seen that there are significant differences for the different configurations, i.e. positions and fixtures, for the air-cooled system. In general, using a fixture increases the time to reach the target temperature and increases the standard deviation. Parallel positioning, i.e. for configurations 1 and 3, seems to be advantageous. However, for normal positioning in the free-standing configuration, a deviation of less than 1 °C is not achieved within the 10 hour resting time.

Figure 6 shows the voltage results after changing the set temperature from 25 °C to 45 °C for configurations 1-4 and 8-9 and different SOC. At 80 % SOC, the measurement results are in good agreement between different setups and configurations. However, very small changes in voltage are observed. At 50 % SOC, more significant voltage changes can be seen. Furthermore, it can be seen that both measurements with the active-cooled system are in good agreement. In contrast, the measurement results for the air-cooled system vary significantly between different configurations. At 30 % SOC, the differences between the air-cooled systems are even more pronounced. For the actively cooled system, both measurements are in good agreement and clearly show a voltage increase. In contrast, the air-cooled system shows significant differences and no clear trend can be observed. Since the measurement results at SOC 80 % show significant measurement uncertainty and the results at SOC 30 % do not show a clear trend, which could also be related to the complex behavior of the LFP, we decided to continue the analysis only at SOC 50 %.

Figure 7 shows the results for the evaluated voltages after 10 h relaxation for configuration 1-4 and 8-9 at the different set temperatures at a SOC of 50 %. The linear regression is also shown as a line. The corresponding voltage gradients and

Table 2: Voltage gradients and corresponding entropy value as evaluated after 10 h of relaxation

Config. Nb.	dV/dT / [$\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$]	Entropy Δs [$\text{J}/(\text{mol K})$]
1	156.94	15.14
2	150.15	14.49
3	150.52	14.52
4	154.74	14.93
8	157.95	15.24
9	156.83	15.13

entropy values are shown in Table 2. It can be seen that all measurements are in very good agreement for determining the entropy after 10 h relaxation.

To summarize the results of the entropy test, it can be said that temperature changes can be performed much faster with an active cooling system. This leads to shorter duration of temperature changes and also to smaller standard deviations of the temperature. It can also be seen that the positioning and mounting of the cell in conventional temperature chambers has a significant influence on both the change in surface temperature and the voltage. However, in terms of time, the advantage of the active cooling system is less pronounced for voltage variation compared to temperature. This could be due to the usual very slow relaxation of the LFP as used in this

study. Finally, all measurement systems lead to similar results for the entropy after 10 h relaxation.

B. HPPC test

Figure 8: Results for the HPPC test for (A) discharge resistance, (B) regen resistance for configurations 1-4,5,8,9 and 11 and (C) temperature increase during the discharge pulse for configurations 1-4,5 and 8.

As a second example, the influence is examined for a HPPC test. Because of cell specifications, the HPPC test profile had to be modified at higher SOC. Therefore, only HPPC results at SOC 10-60 % are evaluated here.

Figure 8 shows the results of the HPPC test. Figure 8(A) shows the calculated discharge resistance for configurations 1-4,5,8,9 and 11. The resistance decreases at higher SOC for all cells and configuration investigated. It can also be seen that

the slope is very similar. However, there are also differences. In particular, for the air-cooled system, a parallel shift between the discharge resistances can be observed. For example, at 10 % SOC, the discharge resistances vary between approximately 1.3 and 1.7 m Ω , with the highest values for configurations 4 and the lowest values for configuration 2. In contrast, the variations between the actively cooled cells are less pronounced. This observation could be related to a more precise temperature control. Note, however, that this can also be affected by the ohmic resistance at the cell connectors.

The results for charge resistance are shown in Figure 8(B). Similar observations can be made here. The differences between the configuration are slightly more pronounced. To evaluate the influence of temperature, the temperature rise during the pulse, i.e. between point 0 and 1 as indicated in Figure 5, is shown in Figure 8(C). No significant temperature changes are observed for the active cooling system. In contrast, small temperature changes are observed for the air-cooled system. The temperature increase is slightly more pronounced for configurations 1 and 4, which have the highest discharge and discharge resistances.

To summarize the results of the HPPC test, significant differences were observed between the air-cooled and the active-cooled systems, while the actively cooled system showed no significant temperature changes during the pulses and no deviation between the measured resistances. This indicates an advantage of the active cooled system in terms of reproducibility. However, we note that a possible higher resistance at the cell connectors could not be excluded in this study and are possible alternative explanations for the observations. Nevertheless, the observations also support the results of the entropy test. In the entropy test, the resistance at the connector is negligible because no current is applied.

C. Fast charge test

The results of the fast charge test are shown in Figure 9. Figure 9(A) shows the voltage of configuration 1-4, 5, 8 and 11 during the fast charge step. The duration of the charge is the same, as specified by the protocol. However, the voltages are shifted between configuration during the charge. The highest voltages, corresponding to the highest overpotentials, are seen for configuration 4. The lowest voltages are observed for configuration 1. No significant differences are observed between the other configurations. It is not surprising that configuration 1 has the highest overvoltage, as it also had the highest discharge and regen resistance during the HPPC test. However, it is surprising that configuration 1 shows the lowest voltages for the fast charge test, as it also showed rather high discharge and regen resistances. A possible explanation can be given using the results shown in Figure 9(B). Here, the average surface temperature is shown for configuration 1-4,9 and 11. For both configuration 1 and 4 there is a significant increase in temperature during the fast charge. Here the temperature increase for configuration 1 is even higher compared to configuration 4. It is possible that the temperature increase during the test resulted in lowered internal resistances within configuration 1, which could explain the low voltages during fast charging. The

Figure 9: Results of the fast charge test with (A) voltage during fast charging for configurations 1-4,5,8,9 and 11 and (B) temperature change during fast charging for configuration 1-4,9 and 11.

temperature of the actively cooled system remains almost constant during the fast charge. As this corresponds to better reproducible test results, it supports the claim of an advantage of an active cooling strategy for battery testing.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have investigated the influence of the cooling strategy on the results of relevant battery tests. In particular, we compared conventional air-cooled systems with an actively cooled system.

In general, the results indicate that the use of an actively cooled system reduces the uncertainty caused by different positions and types of cell mounting. This observation was made for all three tests studied. For the entropy test, it was also observed that the time required to adjust to a different cell surface temperature can be significantly reduced with an active cooling system. However, all of the systems investigated resulted in very similar entropy values for long resting times. For the HPPC and fast charging tests, significant differences were observed for different configurations of the air-cooled system. This could be explained by the influence of temperature, as this was not observed for actively cooled cells. However, the influence of differences in cell connections could not be excluded in this study.

Future studies should further investigate the open questions regarding the influence of the cell connections raised in this article. Other tests, such as dynamic aging tests, should also be investigated. An active cooling system seems to be a promising approach, especially if tests with temperature changes are performed. This is especially promising for the study of path-dependent aging.

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